

Effect of the Central Bank of Nigeria's Agricultural Finance Interventions on Agricultural Output in Nigeria

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Abstract— Agricultural financing is one of the most important ways of developing rural areas in developing countries as it plays an important role in agricultural development. Agricultural financing schemes have played crucial roles in eliminating farmers' financial constraints to invest in farm activities, increasing productivity and improving technologies. This study assesses the effect of Central Bank of Nigeria's agricultural finance interventions on agricultural output in Nigeria from 2010 to 2021. This study adopted the ex-post facto research design as it draws comparison between groups with qualities that already exist and on some dependent variable. This study employed the Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) regression estimate with the aid of Stata 15 econometrics software. The findings revealed that The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF) has positive and significant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria. The study also found that The Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS) has negative and insignificant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria should increase its intervention funds on Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme so as to expand its coverage to the farmers in the rural areas for sustainable growth in agricultural output. Increased CBN interventions in Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme and others is highly recommended to enhance agricultural sector output and the overall growth of the economy.

Keywords— Agricultural financing, ACGSF, CACS, Agricultural Output, ARDLs

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays a key role in every economy, especially the economies of developing countries because it provides the main source of food and income to the rural communities. Agriculture can help reduce poverty, raise incomes and improve food security for 80% of the world's poor, who live in rural areas and work mainly in farming. (World Bank, 2019)

Adamgbe, Belonwu, Ochu and Okafor (2020), opined that agriculture is crucial to economic development through strengthened economic framework, creation of employment, enhancement of farmers' living standard, provision of raw materials to manufacturers, revenue vehicle for government and contribution to gross domestic production of the country.

In the earlier period before 1956, Nigeria's agricultural sector was the greatest contributor to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria. The sector contributed 64.1 percent to GDP and employed over 70 percent of the Nigerian population (Paul, 2015). Furthermore, export of agricultural produce accounted for 80 percent of the country's foreign exchange earnings and 50 percent of government revenue (Okotie, 2018). This was upturned by the discovery of oil in commercial quantity on the 15th of January 1956 in Oloibiri, Bayelsa State. By 1974, shares of petroleum had increased to 45.5% almost doubling that of agriculture which had decreased to 23.4% (Yakub, 2008) and by the 1990s, the share of agricultural products in total exports decreased to less than 2% (Olajide, Akinlabi & Tijani, 2012).

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, despite oil, agriculture remains the base of the Nigerian economy, providing the main source of livelihood for most Nigerians. The agricultural industry contributed approximately 21.42% to nominal GDP in the first quarter 2021. (National Bureau of Statistics Q1 2021 report) Despite being a major contributor to

Nigeria's GDP, the sector still has the potential to increase its share of contribution to GDP and increase its share of total exports.

Analysis by the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) showed that the total amount of estimated untapped potential by 2021 for Nigerian exports of cocoa beans to the ten best markets (Germany, Malaysia, Singapore, Turkey, Netherlands, Italy, Japan, France, Mexico and Indonesia) is around \$425 million. Similarly, the estimated worth of cocoa butter for the top ten markets was put at \$81.9 million, while the value for untapped potential in the market for cocoa paste by 2021 stood at \$6.3 million. Likewise, the untapped market potential for sesame seeds to the top ten markets (China, Japan, South Korea, Mexico, Poland, France, Lebanon, the United States, Canada and the UK) is also estimated at US\$170 million. Overall, agriculture experts are of the view that the country has the potential to generate US\$40 billion annually from export of agricultural goods (PWC 2019).

In recognition of the opportunity's agriculture presents, as well as its importance in driving economic growth, concerted efforts have been made by past and present administrations to improve agricultural productivity in Nigeria. The National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP), launched in 1972 by the Federal Department of Agriculture during the military regime of General Yakubu Gowon, Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), which evolved on May 21, 1976 under the military regime of General Olusegun Obasanjo, the Green Revolution Programme (GRP), which Shehu Shagari launched in April 1980, and Agricultural Development Projects are notable among the agricultural policies and programmes from the 1970s to the present. River Basin-Development Authorities were established in 1976, the National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA) was founded in 1992, the Directorate of Food, Road, and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI) was established in January 1986 under the leadership of General Ibrahim Babangida, and the Better Life Programme (BLP) for rural women was established in 1987 by Mrs. Maryam Babangida, the wife of the then-president of Nigeria. Olusegun Obasanjo launched the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) in 1999; the National Special Programme on Food Security (NSPFS) was introduced in all 36 states of the federation in January 2002; the Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP) was introduced on April 16, 2003; and the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) was introduced in 2011 by former president Jonathan administration.

There are several reasons why these plans and policies have not been successful in increasing agricultural output. Some of these, as mentioned by Kevin (2017), include: lack of participation from all stakeholders; lack of strategy; lack of targets; lack of goals; and lack of specified objectives. It's also crucial to remember that new and better farming techniques must be used if we want to raise productivity in the agricultural industry. The switch to mechanised farming requires a significant investment in capital because it necessitates the acquisition of machinery, instruction of farmers in its operation, and maintenance of such machinery. As a result, one of the most important variables for raising agricultural output is access to money.

It is impossible to overstate the advantages of a healthy agriculture sector for an economy. They include a higher standard of living, a lower import bill, higher foreign exchange revenues, higher farm income, higher GDP, and so on. It makes sense, then, that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has kept its attention on the agriculture industry, as seen by its agricultural initiatives. Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF), Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACCS), Paddy Aggregation Scheme (PAS), Nigeria Incentive-based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL), National Food Security Programme, Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP), The Special FGN Fertiliser Intervention Programme, Accelerated Agricultural Development Scheme (AADS), Agribusiness Small and Medium

Enterprises Investment Scheme (AGSMEIS), and Maize Marketing Scheme are a few of the interventions mentioned, (CBN Development Finance, 2020)

The FAO (2020) posits that even though agriculture remains the largest sector of the Nigerian economy and employs two-thirds of the entire labour force, the production hurdles have significantly stifled the performance of the sector. According to the FAO (2020), Nigeria is estimated to have lost USD 10 billion in annual export opportunity from groundnut, palm oil, cocoa and cotton alone due to continuous decline in the production of these commodities. Some of the challenges noted by the FAO include an outdated land tenure system, a very low level of irrigation development, limited adoption of research findings and technologies, high cost of farm inputs, poor access to credit, inefficient fertilizer procurement and distribution, inadequate storage facilities and poor access to markets, which have all combined to keep agricultural productivity low with high postharvest losses and waste (FAO, 2020)

The need for Nigeria to improve agricultural productivity cannot be overstated. Firstly, agriculture provides an opportunity for Nigeria to diversify from oil. With oil accounting for over 80% of the nation's foreign exchange earnings and about 65% of total government revenue, volatilities in the price of oil have a direct impact on the country's foreign exchange earnings and its ability to fund the annual budget. A typical example was the 2016 economic recession, the first recession in the country since 1991 which was caused by the oil price slump in 2014.

Likewise, the Novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) which was first reported in Wuhan City, China, in December 2019 and declared a pandemic on the 11th of March 2020 by the World Health Organization further exposed Nigeria's vulnerabilities to the price of oil. In a bid to curtail the pandemic, lockdowns/restrictions were imposed in various countries across the globe, which resulted in a sharp decline in the demand and price of oil. The Federal budget for 2020 fiscal year was predicated on an oil price /demand benchmark of \$57 per barrel and 2.18 Million barrels per day, but by the end of March 2020, data from the CBN showed that oil prices declined to as low as US\$17 per barrel, which immediately prompted a revision of the 2020 budget (Ademola, 2019).

Furthermore, Nigeria's population is projected to be about 400 million by 2050, which will make it the third most populous country in the world (PWC 2017). PWC expects food consumption to continue to grow by a minimum of 4% per annum based on the historical average which means food consumption is expected to increase. Nigeria's current rate of consumption has outstripped production with the deficit largely met by importation. PWC (2017) found that on the average, between 2011 and 2015, 1.4 trillion Naira was spent on food imports.

Nigeria's high reliance on importation to meet her agricultural demand is a major cause for concern because exports are largely affected by various trade regimes, some of which may impact negatively on the nation's ability to import. This was demonstrated by export restrictions placed by some countries in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. The International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) reported that about 37 countries had enacted various forms of food export restrictions in response to the pandemic in March 2020, even in countries where average production exceeds domestic consumption. It is therefore imperative that Nigeria becomes self-sufficient in food production to avert a food crisis in the near or distant future, brought about by unexpected global events.

A survey conducted by NOI Polls Limited in November 2016 on agriculture in Nigeria found that in addition to lack of fertilizers, cost of inputs and lack of access to mechanism, one of the major challenges facing the sector is the lack of agricultural credit. So far, the CBN intervention programmes have provided hundreds of billions to smallholder farmers and industrial processors in several key agricultural produce, all aimed at positioning Nigeria to become a self-sufficient food producer (Emefiele, 2020).

These funds are channelled through other financial institutions such as the commercial banks to ensure effective mobilisation of the credit to the agricultural sector. Despite the existence of several financial institutions, credit requirements of farmers are often not met. In most cases delay in disbursement of loans approved constitutes an impediment, causing these loans to reach the farmers after the planting season thereby resulting in diversion and subsequent default.

In order to achieve an optimum level of agricultural productivity, the effect of Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF) interventions in the sector must be ascertained to provide a basis for further interventions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical Review

As a result of resource scarcity, decision makers are continually faced with the burden of efficiently allocating limited resources. In order to effectively allocate resources, measuring productivity becomes paramount.

The study is therefore predicated on economic theories that provide a theoretical framework upon which the study is built.

1. *The Neoclassical Growth Theory*: The Neoclassical growth theory was introduced in 1956 by Robert Solow and Trevor Swan and it postulates that a combination of labour, capital, and technology result in steady economic growth. The Solow-Swan model seeks to explain that varying labour and capital as well as technological advancement will result in stable equilibrium growth. Also, that technological advancement has a major impact on economic growth.

The production function of the neoclassical growth theory used to measure the growth and equilibrium of an economy is $Y = AF(K, L)$

Where;

Y is economy's gross domestic product (GDP)

K denotes its share of capital

L describes the amount of unskilled labour in an economy

A represents a determinant level of technology.

This implies that in order to increase economic growth, (Y) the investment in other factors (K, L) can be increased, given a progressive level of technological advancement. Therefore, based on the Solow-Swan model, the CBN interventions in the agricultural sector should ordinarily have an effect in increasing the growth of the sector, other things being equal.

2. *The Harrod – Domar Model*: A growth model called the Harrod-Domar model was independently created by Roy F. Harrod in 1939 and Evsey Domar in 1946. The concept emphasises capital as a crucial component of economic expansion. According to the model, the economy's savings rate and investment productivity (capital-output ratio) both influence economic growth rates. It places a strong emphasis on savings and investment as the primary drivers of economic growth.
 - i. Based on the model, it can be implied that;
 - ii. Increased capital stimulates economic growth.
 - iii. Investment plays a key role in capital accumulation, which in turn generates productive capacity and income.
 - iv. Economic growth and development in developing countries may be stunted by lack of capital.

Therefore, in order to achieve economic growth, a conscious effort should be made to expand the level of capital in the economy. The Harrod –Domar model has been used widely by developing countries to study the relationship between growth and capital.

This model highlights the importance of capital in economic growth. It therefore provides a justification for CBN interventions in the agricultural sector, as these interventions allow for free flow of capital to the players in the sector.

3. *The Capital-Output Ratio (COR)*: The Capital-Output ratio measures the productivity of capital that has been invested. A low capital output ratio implies that an economy produces a lot of output from little capital, which should be the target for economies.

The model assumes output to be a linear function of capital as:

$$Q = K/V$$

Where

Q = Output

K = Capital stock and;

V = Capital Output ratio.

The Capital Output ratio can be expressed as $V = K/Q$ which basically measures the productivity of capital.

The Key message here is that growth rate can be increased by making more productive investments. The model can be applied to a sector of the economy where growth is targeted. Decision makers can decide how much investment should be allocated to the sector to achieve an expected growth rate based on the estimated value of the capital output ratio.

One major limitation of the Harrod – Domar model however is that it applies to an economy that remains in equilibrium. This implies that labour and capital must always grow at the same rate to maintain the equilibrium state, which is hardly the case. Also, in the Harrod- Domar model, there is no room for the substitutability of labour and capital. Furthermore, the assumption that the capital- output ratio is constant is only reasonable in the short run. This is because in the long run, several factors may affect the efficiency of capital.

4. *Marginal Productivity Theory*: A The marginal productivity theory was advocated by T.H. Von Thunen in 1826 and was advanced further by economists J.B. Clark, Walras, Barone, Ricardo, and Marshall. The Theory explains that under perfect competition, the price of services rendered by a factor of production is equal to its marginal productivity. Accordingly, an increase in the amount of output is attributable to the addition of an extra unit of a factor of production, holding all other factors constant. Marginal productivity is therefore the increase in output resulting from the additional unit of input (factor of production) employed.

The theory assumes the following.

- i. There is perfect competition in product market- market prices of products are not affected by output.
- ii. Perfect competition in factor market- the supply of factors of production is perfectly elasticity.
- iii. Homogeneity of factors- all the factors of production can be substituted for each other.
- iv. Variable input coefficient- the quantity of inputs (factors of production) can be varied.

The marginal product of any of the factors can be calculated as follows.

Marginal Product of one Factor (e.g. Capital) = Change in Total Output / Change in Capital

Where,

Change in Total Output = Old output – New output

Change in Capital = Previous amount of capital - New amount of capital.

The basis of this theory to the study hinges on the assumption that changes in output can be attributed to changes in factors of production such as capital.

The theory was criticized for its limitation on the ability to accurately measure the marginal productivity of a factor of production. This was attributed to the fact that it is impossible to keep other factors of production constant as assumed by the theory. Furthermore, the assumptions of the theory such as perfect competition in the factor and product market are not attainable realistically.

B. Empirical Review

This section is concerned with the review of empirical studies that were carried out by different scholars on topics related to this study. Being one of the major contributors to GDP in Nigeria, the agricultural sector has been one of interest to various researchers.

The economic effects of the Central Bank of Nigeria's agricultural intervention funds were examined by Adamgbe, Belonwu, Ochu, and Okafor in 2020. Since their income and utility gradually improved at a higher rate without intervention than it did with interventions, the study's Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models revealed that poor farmers were worse off with interventions. The study made the recommendation that impoverished farmers should receive targeted, substantial support in order to increase their competitiveness, ensuring they are not displaced by wealthy farm owners, and ensure they have access to markets for fair and competitive pricing.

The impact of agro financing on food production in Nigeria was examined by Osabohien, Adeleye, and De-Alwis (2020). Agro financing is statistically important in explaining the level of food production in Nigeria, according to research using the Johansen and Canonical Cointegration techniques. The research suggests, among other things, allocating more money to the agricultural industry with lenient lending requirements and allocating more arable land for cultivation.

The success of the Nigerian agricultural sector was evaluated by Uzomba, Nikade, and Otokutu (2020) based on contributions made by agricultural funding. The study used the Ordinary Least Square method of regression analysis, and it was discovered that total public spending and agricultural credits are significantly and favourably related to crop, livestock, and fish production, while FDI continues to have a negative relationship with these sectors. According to the report, the government should strengthen its programme for agricultural credit guarantees and spend more money in this area.

Onoh (2020) used the Ordinary Least Square method of regression analysis to assess the relationship between agricultural financing and economic growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2016. In contrast to agricultural sector output, interest rates, and commercial bank loans to the agricultural sector, the study indicated that the Agricultural loans Guarantee Scheme Fund had a considerable impact on real gross domestic product (RGDP). Therefore, it was advised that the government devise a method of allocating funds such that actual farmers would receive them with a very low interest rate.

The effect of commercial banks' loans on Nigeria's agricultural development was studied by Okafor (2020). Unit Root and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method were used in the investigation. The study discovered that while high interest rates have a negative and insignificant impact on agricultural output, credit to the agricultural sector, government spending in the agricultural sector, and the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund (ACGSF) have positive and significant impacts on agricultural output. Additionally, it was suggested that a portion of the losses made by deposit money banks when they lend to the agricultural sector be taken on by the Central Bank of Nigeria. This will increase the lending banks' confidence and motivate them to extend credit to the industry, increasing agricultural productivity.

In their assessment of the impact of institutional funding on the expansion of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, Iwedi, Okey-Nwala, Ibebi, and Nwosi (2020) provided some context. The

study found that the estimated model's relative statistics indicate evidence of a substantial, positive, and significant relationship between the agricultural credit guarantee scheme and the expansion of Nigeria's agricultural industry. This relationship was discovered using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique. In accordance with the study's recommendations, the government should increase the amount of money accessible to farmers under the agricultural loan guarantee programme.

Ndife (2020) examined how the Central Bank of Nigeria's development finance affected the expansion of the country's agriculture industry. The results of the study, which used the Ordinary Least Square method of regression analysis, show a positive association between credit for cash crop cultivation and the expansion of the agricultural industry. Similar to this, a favourable association between loans issued for food crop growing and the expansion of the agricultural sector of the Nigerian economy was also discovered. The growth of the agricultural sector of the economy was not significantly impacted by credit to fisheries and livestock husbandry. The study recommends that the government should strengthen the mechanism and processes through which the credits are delivered and also broaden the scope and availability of such credits for maximum impact.

Evbuomwan, Okoye, and Eke (2020) assessed the impact of public and private financing on Nigeria's agricultural sector. The study used the Ordinary Least Square method of regression analysis, and it was discovered that while Federal Government capital expenditure allocated to the sector did not, loans made to farmers under the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme, commercial banks' credit to the agricultural sector, and Federal Government recurrent expenditure allocated to the sector did. It was recommended that all policies put in place by the Monetary and Fiscal Authorities to encourage the flow of funds to the agricultural sector be sustained and that the Federal Government overhaul its capital budgetary processes and provisions in order to have a positive impact on the development of the sector, especially given that the price of crude oil has been declining over the last four years, which has had a negative impact on Nigeria's economy.

One cannot overstate how important the agriculture sector is to the growth of any economy. The agriculture sector has drawn the interest of numerous scholars because it is one of the main contributors to Nigeria's GDP.

The effect of agricultural financing on the Nigerian economy was assessed by Ademola (2019). utilising secondary data and the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) econometric approach. According to the model's output, resources controlled by commercial and specialised financial institutions will be utilised to finance investments more effectively. According to the report, maintaining credible macroeconomic policies that are pro-investment in modernising the agricultural sector and the debt-equity exchange option are essential for economic growth that is driven by agriculture.

A study on loans and agricultural productivity among farmers in Kano State, Nigeria's Gwarzo Local Government Area, was undertaken by Hamidan (2019). To assess the collected data, the study used descriptive statistics, the Pearson Linear Correlation Coefficient, and content analysis. The results showed that farmers' productivity levels are negatively impacted by a lack of access to agricultural loans. According to the study, financial institutions should intervene in agriculture more often. It also suggested that these financial institutions make sure that farmers in rural areas

have easy access to credit and are well supervised to make the best use of the facilities and therefore increase production.

Ayinde, et al, (2018) appraised the assessment of Central Bank intervention on rice production in Kwara State, Nigeria with a special focus on the Anchor Borrower's Program. The study employed descriptive and inferential statistics such as percentage and mean, binary logistic regression, average treatment effect and likert-type scale and the findings reveal that 88.1% of the beneficiaries breached the agreement and refuse to deliver their produce to the Anchor Borrowers' Programme due to some reasons and their average estimated yield per hectare of paddy rice for all beneficiaries was 3.94 metric tons per hectare. The study recommended that the governments must intervene with subsidized lending (seeking no profit, amortizing high transaction costs, spreading the risk on a national basis), since most borrowers in rural areas are small farmers.

The impact of the Anchor Borrower Programme on agricultural commodity prices and job creation in Kebbi State, Nigeria, was evaluated by Saheed, Alexander, Isa, and Adeneye (2018). Multiple regression analysis was used in conjunction with interviews and a structured questionnaire to discover the impact of Anchor Borrower Programmes (ABP) support for farmers on agricultural commodity prices (ACP) and employment generation (EMPG) in the Kebbi state agricultural sector, particularly in Argungu LGA. According to the report, the Anchor Borrower Programme policy in Nigeria should be supported and periodically reviewed in order to increase the opportunities for job creation and stabilise the price of agricultural commodities in Kebbi state, particularly in Argungu LGA.

The effect of credits on agricultural output in Nigeria was evaluated by Enilolobo and Ode-Omenka (2018). The results of the study showed that there is no long-run association between deposit money bank credit to the farm sector in Nigeria and agriculture sector output. This was determined by using the Johansen cointegration test and Multivariate Ordinate Least Squares regression estimation. According to the report, deposit money banks should lower their interest rates when making loans to businesses in the agriculture sector in order to stimulate borrowing by the industry and strengthen the agricultural sector.

Dumoteim (2018) investigated how the Central Bank of Nigeria's actions in development finance affected Nigerian agriculture. This study used a descriptive research approach and a questionnaire to gather data, and it reveals that the initiatives have made some progress. Expanding the interventions' reach, involving all relevant parties, improving monitoring and evaluation, and building the capacity of the Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) to take more active roles are all suggested as ways to further boost agricultural output.

In Nigeria, the effect of credit availability on agricultural production was studied by Anetor et al. in 2016. The study used a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, and it was discovered that while commercial loans to the agricultural sector had a considerable impact on agricultural production, the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGS) fared poorly in explaining agricultural sector performance. The report suggests that by providing lending facilities at interest rates below market, the government could encourage commercial banks to finance investments in the agricultural sector.

Wagan, et al. (2016) assessed the importance of agricultural finance in Pakistan's rural and agricultural growth. Primary data were used to inform the study. A thorough and well-designed questionnaire was created for data collection, and it was used to interview both borrowers and non-borrowers of agricultural financing. A timely supply of the inputs needed for agricultural production was discovered to be made possible by agricultural finance for farmers. The report urges policymakers to guarantee that farmers receive as much credit as they require at subsidised interest rates and the need for agricultural financing programmes that make it simple for farmers to access agricultural finance.

C. Theoretical framework

The theoretical underpin of this study is the marginal productivity theory advocated by T.H. Von Thunen in 1826 and was advanced further by economists J.B. Clark, Walras, Barone, Ricardo, and Marshall. The Theory explains that under perfect competition, the price of services rendered by a factor of production is equal to its marginal productivity. Accordingly, an increase in the amount of output is attributable to the addition of an extra unit of a factor of production, holding all other factors constant. Marginal productivity is therefore the increase in output resulting from the additional unit of input (factor of production) employed.

The theory assumes the following.

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The theory was criticized for its limitation on the ability to accurately measure the marginal productivity of a factor of production. This was attributed to the fact that it is impossible to keep other factors of production constant as assumed by the theory. Furthermore, the assumptions of the theory such as perfect competition in the factor and product market are not attainable realistically.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Model Specification

The model for this study was structured in line with the work of Evbuomwan, Okoye and Eke (2020) that evaluated the effect of government and private sector financing on the agricultural sector in Nigeria. The study employed Ordinary Least Square method of Regression Analysis modelled in the form; $Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_i + \mu_i + \beta X_t + \varepsilon_t$(I)

Where Y is agricultural sector output and X represents vectors of explanatory variables.

They found that loan granted to farmers under the agricultural credit guarantee scheme, commercial banks' credit to the agricultural sector and Federal Government recurrent expenditure allocated to the sector impacted it positively, while the Federal Government capital expenditure allocated to the sector did not. It was recommended that all the policies should be put in place by the Monetary and Fiscal Authorities to encourage flow of funds to the agricultural sector be sustained and that the Federal Government should overhaul its capital budgetary processes and provisions so as to make a positive impact on the development of the sector, particularly since crude oil price has been on the decline in the last four years impacting Nigeria's economy negatively.

The Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method adopted was used to specify the model for this study. It is an economic model of simple regression analysis that shows the relationship between the variables examined in this research. The model in its structural form is stated as follows:

$$RGDP_A = f(ACGSF, CACS) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Its econometric form is linearly stated from the model of equation (1) to become:

$$RGDP_A = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACGSF + \beta_2 CACS + \mu \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The ARDL model has been explicitly stated as:

$$\Delta RGDP_{A_t} = a_1 + \beta_{11} \Delta RGDP_{A_{t-1}} + \beta_{12} \Delta ACGSF_{t-1} + \beta_{13} \Delta CACS_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{11} \Delta RGDP_{A_{t-1}} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{12} \Delta ACGSF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{13} \Delta CACS_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

Where;

$RGDP_A$ = Agricultural Contributions to Real Gross Domestic Product

$ACGSF$ = Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund

$CACS$ = Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme

β_0 is a constant

β_1 , and β_2 are parameters to be estimated

μ = Error term

From the model, the Agricultural Contributions to Real Gross Domestic Product ($RGDP_A$) is the dependent variable. The independent variables in the model are *Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF)* and *Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS)*. Data collected on these represent the outcome of the impact of the Central Bank of Nigeria's interventions on agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

1. *Apriori Expectation:* $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$.

The evaluation therefore is based on whether the coefficient conforms to the economic postulations. The expected relationship is that the outcome of Central Bank of Nigeria's interventions should have a significant effect on agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A. Presentation of Descriptive Statistics Theoretical Review

This section presents the descriptive performance of the variables employed in this study. The section looked at the performance analysis of the employed variables within the period under review.

TABLE I
DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VARIABLES EMPLOYED

	RGDP	ACGSF	CACS
Mean	5843.625	192966	7837026905.67
Std. Dev.	2514.038	1024851.	8847656668.62
Skewness	0.871902	0.590190	1.614566
Maximum	11988.58	4443990.	40603000000
Minimum	2594.760	465515.9	0.000000
Jarque-Bera	6.105057	3.801925	35.35432
Probability	0.047239	0.149425	0.000000
Observations	author name	48	48

Source: Extracted from Stata results

Table I above shows the descriptive analysis of the variables employed in this study. From the table, the mean column shows that the mean values of all the variables have positive return. In terms of their performances, the table shows a better performance of the Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS) as the mean score of 7837026905.67 indicated.

Considering consistency in performance, table I above shows that Agricultural contribution to Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDPA) was more consistent in performance than other variables employed in this study. This was proved by the low Standard Deviation value of 2514.038 with respect to its mean value of 5843.625.

Also, the skewness column shows that all the variables of the study have a long right tail. This is because of the positive nature of their outcomes. From the Jarque-Bera analysis, table I shows that only Agricultural contribution to Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDPA) and Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS) were normally distributed as shown by the various Jarque-Bera probability values of 0.047239 and 0.000000 respectively.

B. Unit Root Test Results

The results Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test and Zandrews unit root test with structural breaks are presented in Table II.

TABLE II
ADF UNIT ROOT WITHOUT STRUCTURAL BREAK ZANDREWS UNIT ROOT WITH STRUCTURAL BREAK

Variable	Levels(Cons&Trend)	1 st diff(Cons&Trend)	Order of Integration	Levels(Cons &Trend)	1 st diff(Cons&Trend)	Order of Integration
RGDPA	-2.011	-48.812***	I(1)	-4.704** (2017q4)	-	I(0)
ACGSF	-4.421***	-	I(0)	-2.479 (2013q1)	-13.132*** (2018q1)	I(1)
CACS	-3.810***	-	I(0)	-2.909 (2017q3)	-8.972*** (2017q2)	I(1)

Source: Extract from Regression Printout using Stata 15

*Note: The statistics reported are the t - Statistics with the associated break dates in brackets. Agricultural contribution to Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDPA), Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF) and Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS). ***, **, * signify 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively. Values in “()” are the break dates revealed by the unit root tests with structural break. Zandrews Unit root Critical values: 1%: -4.93 5%: -4.42 10%: -4.11. ADF Critical values at levels: -3.668 -2.966 -2.616 @ 1% 5% 10% resp. ADF Critical values at 1st Diff: -3.675 -2.969 -2.617@ 1% 5% 10% respectively.*

The results in table II indicate different orders of integration for the time-series variables. Specifically, ACGSF and CACS were stationary at levels with ADF while RGDPA were stationary at first difference. RGDPA was stationary at levels with Zandrews test while ACGSF and CACS were stationary at first difference. This makes the time-series variables unsuitable for conventional cointegration methods which require the same order of integration for cointegration analysis, such as those proposed by Johansen (1995). However, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds cointegration method suffices at this juncture because it allows for different orders of integration.

C. ARDL Bounds Cointegration Test Results

TABLE III
ARDL BOUND CO-INTEGRATION

Estimated Model	F-Statistics	
	K_3	1.762
Critical Values	Lower Bound I(0)	Upper Bound I(1)
1%	5.15	6.36
5%	3.79	4.85
10%	3.17	4.14

Source: Authors' computation using Stata 15.

In Table III, the bounds test statistic (1.762) was found to have fallen below the lower-bound (3.79) at the 5% level of significance and therefore resulted to the acceptance of the null hypothesis of “no cointegration”. Based on this result, a “restricted” error correction model was estimated alongside the long-run and short-run model as seen in Tables IV.

As a starting point, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and optimal lag of (2 1 2) was used as the optimal lag-specification for the ARDL model.

D. The Long and Short Run ARDL Model for RGDP Model Specification

TABLE IV
SHORT AND LONG RUN LINEAR ARDL RESULTS

Variables	Linear ARDL Without Structural Break	
	Short-run	Long-run
ECT	-0.303 (0.033**)	-
D.RGDPA	0.398 (0.000***)	- 0.527 (0.069*)
LACGSF	-0.054 (0.123)	0.066 (0.616)
LCACS		

Source: Extract from Regression Printout using Stata 15

***, **, * signify 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively. ECT is the error correction term that is expected to be negative and statistically significant. The statistics reported are the parameters with the associated probability values in brackets

E. Discussion of Findings

In the error correction model, table IV, interest lies in the error correction term (ECT_{t-1}) which appears to be expectedly negative and statistically significant at the 5% level (based on its p -value (0.033)). Its magnitude (-0.303) indicates a moderate rate of adjustment to long-run equilibrium and specifically implies that approximately 30.3% of all discrepancies in long-run equilibrium will be corrected in each period.

On the other hand, in the long-run model, ACGSF unexpectedly have a negative relationship with RGDP although significant at 10%. CACS has a positive and insignificant relationship with RGDP in the long run. While a unit increase in CACS will increase RGDP, a unit increase in ACGSF will lead to a decrease in RGDP.

In short run, the coefficient of ACGSF is expectedly positive and significant. This implies that ACGSF is a positive and significant determinant of RGDP. A unit increase in ACGSF will lead to an increase in RGDP in the period under consideration. The results show that CACS has a negative and insignificant relationship with RGDP. A unit increase in CACS leads to a decrease in RGDP.

F. Post Estimation Diagnosis

1. *Autocorrelation Test Result:* To check if the specification suffers from autocorrelation problem, the Breusch-Godfrey (BG) Serial Correlation Lagrange Multiplier (LM) statistic was used. The null hypothesis of the test is that there is no serial correlation in the residuals up to the specified lag order. The BG-LM serial correlation test reported in Table V shows that the F-statistic value of 18.06009 has a significant p -value of 0.000. This study, therefore, rejects the null hypothesis.

TABLE V
DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VARIABLES EMPLOYED

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	18.06009	Prob. F(2,43)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	21.91310	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000

Source: Extracted from Stata results

2. **Heteroscedasticity Test Result:** Bruserch –Pagan-Godfrey (BPG) test, and White test were employed in this study for Heteroscedasticity. This test is conducted in order to ascertain that the disturbance or the errors has the same variance such that OLS estimators are best leaner unbiased error (BLUE), that is the coefficient estimates are efficient, consistent and unbiased. This test states that if the P-value is significant at 95% confidence interval, the data has heteroscedasticity problem, whereas if the p value is insignificant (greater than 0.05), the data has no heteroscedasticity problem. In this study as shown in Table V and Table VI, both the F-statistic and Chi-Square versions of the test statistic gave the same conclusion that there is no evidence for the presence of heteroscedasticity, since the p-values were more than 0.05.

TABLE VI
HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST: BREUSCH-PAGAN-GODFREY AND WHITE

Residual Diagnostic tests	
Type of test	Prob.
Heteroskedasticity Test: White	0.1450
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.3086

Source: Extracted from Stata results

3. **Normality Test Result:** In statistics, the normality tests are used in order to determine whether a given set of data is well-defined by a normal distribution. Histogram of residuals and the Jarque–Bera test were used to determine normality. Figure 1 showed that Jarque-Bera statistic had a P-value of 0.047239 implying that the probability is less than 5% therefore the data were normally distributed.

Fig. 1 Normality Test Result

4. *The Breusch-Godfrey Statistics:* The Breusch Godfrey statistic value of 0.0000 indicates no presence of auto-correlation in the model and hence of no or little effect on the estimates and inference made about them by the statistical tests.
5. *Test of Stability:* The stability test was carried out using the Eigen value stability condition. All the Eigen values of the variables lie inside the unit circle indicating that the variables used for the study satisfy stability condition.

Fig. 2 Stability Test Results

E. Discussion of Findings

This study to assess the effect of Central Bank of Nigeria's agricultural finance interventions on agricultural output in Nigeria. To ensure that the aim is achieved, this study appraised the effect of Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACs) on agricultural development in Nigeria.

After the analysis of the data presented in table IV, the following were the findings of this study:

- a. The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF) has a positive and significant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.
- b. The Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACs) has a negative and insignificant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.

The findings of this study support the views of Anetor, Ogbechie, Kelikume and Ikpesu (2016) whose study found Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) to have performed fairly in explaining agricultural sector performance. More so, Anetor, et. al. (2016) found commercial loans to agricultural sector had no significant impact on agricultural production.

The study of Oyakhilomen and Zibah (2014) found an insignificant relationship existing between Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and the growth of Nigerian economy. However, the study also found an insignificant and negative relationship between Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS) and the growth of Nigerian economy. These findings explained that despite the amount of funds injected by the Federal Government of Nigeria, it seems that the agricultural finance interventions had no effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

The agricultural development seems to be an inevitable stylized fact of development, characterized largely by major changes in agricultural land and especially labour productivity. Farmers' decisions to invest and to produce are closely influenced by access to financial instruments. If appropriate risk mitigation products are lacking, or if available financial instruments do not match farmers' needs, farmers may be discouraged to adopt better technologies, to purchase agricultural inputs, or to make other decisions that can improve the efficiency of their businesses. Improving access to finance can increase farmers' investment choices and provide them with more effective tools to manage risks.

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGSF) has a positive effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.
2. The Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACS) has an insignificant effect on agricultural output in Nigeria.

B. Recommendation

In line with the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been made by the researcher:

The Central Bank of Nigeria should increase its intervention funds on Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme so as to expand its coverage to the farmers in the rural areas for sustainable growth in agricultural output.

Increased CBN interventions in Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme and others is highly recommended to enhance agricultural sector output in particular and the overall growth of the economy.

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